

Effective Means of Developing Concentrated Learning Skills in Primary School Students

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Annotation: The means of formation and development of concentrated learning skills in students in this article: development of any skill management scheme, interesting approaches, system of extracurricular and additional education, coordination of the activities of the team of leaders and educators.

Keywords: concentrated learning skills, management, knowledge, community, turner, semantic reading, learning, project, problem situation.

World scientific pedagogical experiments show that arming young people with the skills that serve to be able to acquire professions that are not yet clear, to live well, to overcome the problems that arise is an important problem and the main goal of today.

In the main aspects of modern didactics, the organization of the formation of the concepts of elements of research in schoolchildren and preschool children, the development of concentrated educational skills in schoolchildren and the socio-pedagogical support of teachers for their preparation for this activity were considered.

At the same time, along with scientific research in the field of theory and practice of managing the development of concentrated educational skills in the period under consideration, the creative research of teacher-innovators, as well as their experimental activities aimed at developing their own classification options for pedagogical communities, have practical significance [185; 262]. It should be recognized: despite the fact that these and many other classifications do not have subsequent global systemic development, the pedagogical practice of finding management solutions to the problem of developing concentrated academic skills within the school helps to improve the quality of school education. It is worth noting that modern developers of educational and methodological complexes of various educational disciplines include in the teaching composition simple and complex general learning skills that develop at a certain school age.

The conceptual idea of the formation and development of concentrated learning skills in students adopted in the educational system is that any skills, including educational and methodological actions, are formed in a similar way. At the same time, the development of any skills among schoolchildren is carried out through the following management scheme:

1. Formation of the concept of character.
2. Initial application experience.
3. Awareness of the need to master the skill.
4. Mastering the methods of performing actions.
5. Active learning (with the help of knowledge, self-control and error correction).

6. Examination of the student's ability to perform an action [185].

It should be noted that even in the pedagogical practice of teachers of primary education, in particular in native language lessons, the use of various methodologies, combined with management and methodological solutions, makes a holistic didactic and methodological resource meta-subjects an effective tool for the development of concentrated learning skills in primary school students.

There are also interesting approaches to the development of concentrated learning skills in elementary students, in which the classification of concentrated learning skills has been carried out. In particular, the researcher expressed the experience of the formation of concentrated learning skills through the Educational Sciences of mathematics and the native language [254, 1162-1165-b.].

Extracurricular activities and the system of further education play an important role in the development of concentrated learning skills in schoolchildren. Differences from all other forms of intellectual competition in educational projects in additional training of students include:

- teamwork-the team is always stronger, it is possible to achieve better results together;
- tournament is an active and controversial form of intellectual competitions in which participants learn to correctly formulate questions and ask them online;
- at all stages, students participate under the guidance of a team mentor whose mission is clear;
- possibility of developing tournament tasks mustakil;
- Tournament is a kind of platform for developing the culture of ways of interacting students, and so on [279].

For our research in the experience presented, it is essential that competition organizers offer management assistance that allows students to develop all skills at the creative level, including: willingness to act in non-standard situations [279].

All of the above indicates that the development of concentrated O'oeuvre skills in the study requires support for Bashkir supply. In our study, such a supply took the form of management technology. The management cycle was logically implemented in the development of technology for managing the development of concentrated learning skills in student research activities [103; 104].

The development of technology for managing the development of research elements in students with concentrated learning skills is based on various management activities, differing in composition, specific purposefulness, individual structure and complex functionality [103; 104]. It is known that management technology ensures the consistent execution of a set of standardized processes and actions included in them, which, in turn, provided for by the appropriate tools of management activity (norms, rules, a set of requirements) [37].

The procedure for teaching in native language lessons is defined as a group of actions, and the following signs are laid on the basis of its integration:

- uniform designation;
- implicit sequence in implementation;
- desired reciprocal motion;
- relative completion;
- Multiple use of given procedures [37].

The following important features of pedagogical technology of comprehensive study and analysis of pedagogical technologies in education were identified, promoting the coordination and continuity of the activities of the heads of schools and the team of educators in order to develop concentrated learning skills

in the research activities of students:

- high-level guarantee of obtaining a programmed result;
- based on surveys of participants in educational relations;
- the possibility of using information and communication technology tools, modern e-learning resources, project management methods;
- ensure consistency of procedures and actions;
- the relationship of management procedures and their structural actions;
- detailed methodological and resource support of every action of the procedure;
- relevance for the use of all levels of general education in educational activities;
- ease of distribution and application in educational activities;
- striving for a maksadi to solve complex problems at different levels and in different social situations;
- dynamism, high level of commonality and adaptation to changing conditions of the socio-cultural environment;
- The effectiveness of making decisions aimed at eliminating unnecessary duplication.

These characteristics or advantages were taken into account in the development and testing of technology for managing the development of concentrated skills of research elements in schoolchildren.

In elementary education, the invariant bases of performing educational-methodological actions at the border of the Interdisciplinary Program should be formed. With this approach, as a result of studying all subjects without exception at the stage of primary education, personal, regulatory, cognitive and communicative universal educational actions are formed as the basis of the ability of graduates to learn. The startup is focused on information communication technologies (ICT) as its tools in the school, educational and methodological action formation program [200, p.77]. At the same time, it is recommended to use ICT tools in assessing the formation of universal educational actions in the space of the information and educational environment of the school, where teachers and students plan and implement their activities and results [200, P.78].

Obviously, the various circumstances established in the state educational standard help to effectively implement the specific aspects of our research, the basics of Educational Research are a prerequisite for the effective development of concentrated educational skills in the research activities of students of grades 5-10 in the meta-science course. The state educational standard of Higher Education as a tool for the development of universal educational actions in primary education distinguishes educational situations (specific to science and science) suitable for the development of universal educational actions in qualification requirements [201, P.125]. Various training situations are also offered: from problem - to training - situation [201, P.125]. The Universal educational action Development Program in Primary Education describes various forms of extracurricular activities, including the organization of educational and research activities for schoolchildren to develop universal educational actions [201, pp. 131-142]. It is worth noting that in sources that include programs for the formation and development of universal educational actions of primary and secondary school students [93; 264], giving general recommendations on the formation and development of universal learning actions, taking into account the age characteristics and specific aspects of the students' subjects. Typical tasks aimed at assessing the formation and development of Universal educational actions are presented. We take all the tools listed above to develop students' research activities in planned and extracurricular activities in native language classes with concentrated learning skills.

DTS provides a prerequisite for the purposeful formation and development of universal learning actions as a result of meta-subject learning, at the same time, these conditions are described through the main tasks of universal educational actions [93, 27-28-b.]. In fact, the formation and development of universal

educational actions is carried out within the framework of all educational disciplines.

At the same time, the main cases that ensure the use of universal educational actions in the formation of research elements of schoolchildren should be carried out in the process of implementing meta-science courses.

It should be recognized that students of the Modern School of general education will feel a sense of autonomy for holistic collections of didactic, methodological and managerial materials that provide the development of concentrated learning skills in the subject of the native language.

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